

SMART SOLAR STREET LIGHT WITH POWER SAVER

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ABSTRACT: All in One Solar Street light is a compact integrating Solar panels, LED light, Battery, RTC, Arduino, Gas sensor and a PIR motion sensor. Due to its compact size, this light can be easily mounted on pole top by anyone. Light is operated on automatically with using RTC. The light has automatic dusk to dawn operation and needs negligible maintenance once installed. The All-in-One Solar Street light uses high quality material and is designed for Indian environments. They also provide external Theft Protection for solar kit and indication are provided by Buzzer.

Key words: Solar Panel, Battery, ATmega328, TC, PIR Sensor, pollution Sensor, Theft Protection.

I. INTRODUCTION

All In One Solar Street light is a compact integrating Solar panels, LED light, Rechargeable Battery, RTC, Arduino, Gas sensor and a PIR motion sensor. All In One Solar Street light uses a PIR motion sensor to adjust the LED light brightness intelligently. On detecting any movement in 12m radius around the light, the LED glows at full brightness. If no movement is detected for more than 1 minute, the brightness is reduced to one-third. This intelligent brightness control coupled with maintenance free Rechargeable battery technology provides longer backup time and better battery life. Due to its compact size, this light can be easily mounted on pole top by anyone. The light has automatic dusk to dawn operation and needs negligible maintenance once installed. The All-in-One Solar Street light uses high quality material and is designed for Indian environments. It even gives indication to the user that the

Solar panel is alert form theft.

Fig-1. System Configuration of solar street light

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

Solar panel are charging the battery within time and battery is overcharge then relay circuit to cut off the supply.

Using RTC light is ON at night time, in midnight light operated using motion sensor. Also using pollution sensor to indicate pollution on environment and emergency signal. They are providing external Theft protection.

Fig-2: Block Diagram of All-in-One Solar Street Light

Fig -3: Solar panel

III. COMPONENTS OF THE SYSTEM Solar Panel

A solar panel is a collection of solar cells. The solar panel converts the solar energy into electrical energy. Output of the solar panel is its power which is measured in terms of Watts or Kilowatts. Solar power uses multiple reflectors to collect more sun's thermal energy. Thermal energy collected through the day to perform different operations. Performance of the solar panel depends on a number of factors like climate, conditions of the sky, orientation of the panel, intensity and duration of sunlight and its wiring connections.

In solar street lights, the solar panel is one of the most important parts, and it is also known as solar photovoltaic cell. These cells are of two types: poly crystalline and mono crystalline. Compare to the polycrystalline, monocrystalline conversion rate is higher. solar panels use light energy from the sun used to convert solar energy into electricity.

Electrical connections are made in series to accomplish an output voltage and to provide a current facility connections are made in parallel. The majority of modules use silicon or wafer based crystalline silicon but most of these solar panels are inflexible.

Rechargeable Battery

Rechargeable battery is a type of electrical battery or accumulator and its electro mechanical reactions are reversible so it is called as secondary cell. Usually, there are two types of batteries: lead acid battery and gel cell deep cycle battery.

In solar LED street lights, a battery is used to store electricity from the solar panel during the day time to provide energy in the night time. The capacity and lifetime of the battery is very important as they affect the backup power days of the lights.

Fig -4: Rechargeable Battery

ATMega328p

The ATMega328P provides the following features: 32Kbytes of In-System Programmable Flash with Read- While-Write capabilities, 1k Bytes EEPROM, 2K bytes SRAM, 23 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, Real Time Counter (RTC), three

flexible Timer/Counters with compare modes and PWM, 1 serial programmable USARTs , 1 byte-oriented 2-wire Serial Interface (I2C), a 6- channel 10-bit ADC (8 channels in TQFP and QFN/MLF packages) , a programmable Watchdog Timer with internal Oscillator, an SPI serial port, and six software selectable power saving modes. The Idle mode stops the CPU while allowing the SRAM, Timer/Counters, SPI port, and interrupt system to continue functioning. The Power-down mode saves the register contents but freezes the Oscillator, disabling all other chip functions until the next interrupt or hardware reset. In Power-save mode, the asynchronous timer continues to run, allowing the user to maintain a timer base while the rest of the device is sleeping. The ADC Noise Reduction mode stops the CPU and all I/O modules except asynchronous timer and ADC to minimize switching noise during ADC conversions. In Standby mode, the crystal/resonator oscillator is running while the rest of the device is sleeping. This allows very fast start-up combined with low power consumption. In Extended Standby mode, both the main oscillator and the asynchronous timer continue to run.

Fig -5: ATMega328p

Motion Sensor

The PIR motion sensor is ideal to detect movement. PIR stand for “Passive Infrared”. Basically, the PIR motion sensor measures infrared light from objects in its

field of view. So, it can detect motion based on changes in infrared light in the environment. It is ideal to detect if a human has moved in or out of the sensor range.

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Fig -6: Motion Sensor

The sensor in the figure above has two built-in potentiometers to adjust the delay time (the potentiometer at the left) and the sensitivity (the potentiometer at the right).

RTC

This tiny RTC module is based on the clock chip DS1307 which supports the I2C protocol. It uses a Lithium cell battery (CR1225). The clock/calendar provides seconds, minutes, hours, day, date, month, and year information. The end of the month date is automatically adjusted for months with fewer than 31 days, including corrections for leap year. The clock operates in either the 24-hour or 12- In over project we require time for ON the street light lamp in normal mode operation (6:00pm to 10:00pm) and after this we switch the PIR motion sensor detection motion in that area an ON/OFF lamp up to

(11:00pm to 5:00am). And after 5.00am hole system is fully OFF.It is continuous process to every day.

PIR Motion Sensor operate LED Array

Fig -7: RTC

IV. CONCLUSION

The project entitled “All in One Solar Street Light” mainly gives an idea in saving power consumption by various devices in any field. Since it can switch automatically in reference to real time it doesn’t waste power. Usually most of the street lights run on the power generated by several power plants using lots of resources. This project is designed in order to use the natural power generated from solar rays. Also, it consumes very less power and works for a long time.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mohd Heikal Husin, "Smart Street Lighting Systems Using IoT Technologies", October 2019.
- [2] Rakhi Joshi, "Solar Powered Smart Street Light with Automatic Control System", June 2020.
- [3] Ganiyu R. A., "Embedded Systems for Smart Lighting Applications", July 2019.
- [4] S. Kumar and P. Singh, "Energy Efficient Solar Street Lighting System Using PIR Sensor", March 2023.
- [5] A. Sharma and R. Gupta, "Design of Automatic Street Light System Using Solar Power and Motion Detection", January 2024.

[6] K. Ramesh and V. Reddy, "IoT Based Smart Street Light Monitoring System", August 2023.

[7] "Street Light Control System Using Arduino and PIR Sensor", http://www.tutorialspoint.com/arduino/arduino_pir_sensor.htm

[8] Usha Rani & Ramya Krishna, "Overview of Smart Lighting Systems Using Renewable Energy", November 2014.

[9] M. Patel, "Automatic Street Lighting System with Solar Power and Sensors", February 2024.

[10] R. Verma and S. Khan, "Energy Efficient LED Street Light System Using PIR Sensor", May 2023.